

This document forms section four of the University of Bath's Responsible Research Assessment Guidance and should be read alongside [the full guidance](#). You can find more information on the [RRA webpage](#).

4. Assessing research outputs – untangling three facets of quality

Key points covered in this section:

Research outputs can be assessed against three core facets of quality:

- **Contribution:** the specific contribution that an individual made to the research.
- **Quality of content:** evaluation of the novelty, significance, rigour, ethic and integrity of the research.
- **Influence, impact, visibility and reach:** the impact or potential impact the research output had within its field and/or wider world.

A core criterion for the assessment of a research output is its quality. However, definitions of research quality are complex and often contested. This section untangles the concept of quality and proposes three core facets to consider when assessing research outputs.

1. Contribution

Assess the contribution that the individual made to the research output. Understanding their input is an important first step to understanding the merit that should be attributed to it. This is straightforward for single-author outputs but for multi-author outputs, everyone's contribution will need to be more carefully considered.

2. Quality of content

Evaluate the novelty, significance, and rigour of the research. Is the research design appropriate, ethical, and performed with integrity?

3. Impact, influence, visibility, and reach

Consider what impact or potential impact the research output had within its field and/or wider world.

Often, research metrics that imply visibility, impact or reach (such as number of citations) are used as quick proxies for quality of content. This is not a reliable proxy. Citations could be positive or negative (for example, contesting poor quality work).

Raw citation counts also vary widely between disciplines, meaning they are often not comparable between fields even within the same department.

It is important we clearly define what constitutes the 'best available evidence' when assessing each of the three facets of quality, and equally, to identify which types of evidence are unhelpful.

To learn more about the evidence that can and cannot be used to assess each of the three facets, see section 5, Evidencing Quality.

For more information read [the full guidance](#) or visit the [RRA webpage](#).